

Dealing with Emotional Requirements for Software Ecosystems: Findings and Lessons Learned in the PHArA-ON Project

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Abstract. Requirements Engineering (RE) stands as the cornerstone in ensuring that a system comprehensively captures and analyzes the needs and expectations of its users and stakeholders. Despite the numerous approaches designed for dealing with functional and quality (non-functional) requirements, approaches for dealing with emotional requirements still lag. Emotional requirements capture how users should feel when using a system, and inadequate consideration of such requirements results in end-users reluctance to use the system. In this paper, we report on our experience in dealing with emotional requirements as part of an H2020 European Project, namely PHArA-ON (Pilots for Healthy and Active Ageing in Europe) for the development of the PHArA-ON ecosystem that aims at improving the well-being and active aging of older adults. Specifically, we present the process we followed for dealing with emotional requirements, and we summarize the findings and lessons learned from this experience.

Keywords: Emotional Requirements · Emotions · Goal Modeling · Ecosystems · Requirements Engineering

1 Introduction

The success of any software system relies on its ability to fulfill the needs and expectations of its stakeholders [1]. These needs and expectations serve as a key source for specifying the requirements for the system [2]. In the Requirements Engineering (RE) community, requirements traditionally fall into two categories: functional and non-functional (quality) requirements, both of which a successful system must satisfactorily address. Engineering methodologies have evolved

to adeptly manage functional and various types of quality requirements (e.g., usability, reliability [3]). However, emotional requirements, despite their significance, have remained relatively underexplored within the RE community [4].

Emotions are inherently complex, involving cognitive appraisals, physiological responses, and behavioral tendencies [5]. Although emotions can be broadly classified under positive (e.g., happiness and relaxation) and negative (e.g., anger and stress) emotions [6], recent studies have suggested that most emotions encompass elements of both positivity and negativity [7], which results in ambiguity and conflicts in interpreting emotions [8], rendering the task of capturing and understanding emotions highly challenging. On the other hand, emotional requirements capture how users should feel when using the system [9,6]. For example, a user might want to feel motivated and empowered while avoiding feelings of anxiety, stress, or frustration during system interaction. Accordingly, inadequate consideration of such requirements can result in end-users reluctance to use the system [3]. Specifically, even a flawlessly functional system might face rejection if it fails to resonate with the emotional needs of its users [3].

Emotional requirements/needs can be highly relevant to other functional and quality requirements, i.e., they can influence and/or can be influenced by several functional and quality requirements. In this context, capturing and addressing the emotional requirements of end users during the early phases of a system design is essential for a successful system. This also improves system acceptance and usability on the users' side [3]. However, this is not an easy task as existing approaches for dealing with emotional requirements (e.g., [4,3]) are relatively scarce, they capture emotional requirements a high level of abstraction and predominantly focus on elicitation, as revealed by a recent mapping study [6]. Moreover, available approaches were not designed to fit the needs of ecosystems, which are large software systems/platforms that consist of various, constantly interacting, and partly autonomous subsystems [10]. Ecosystems have a considerable number of stakeholders such as internal and external developers, domain experts, and various types of end-users, which makes specifying their requirements a very challenging task [11].

In this paper, we report on our experience in dealing with emotional requirements within the PHArA-ON ecosystem under the larger context of the PHArA-ON project. Our primary contribution lies in presenting a comprehensive process tailored specifically for handling emotional requirements. The process is composed of several activities accompanied by rules and suggestions that need or are advised to be followed respectively. This guarantees that the activities will be conducted while leaving sufficient flexibility to cope with any emergent situations. We aimed to create an easily replicable process, providing detailed descriptions for each activity to facilitate seamless adoption by others. The process has been followed across six different pilot⁵ sites for capturing⁶, prioritizing, and validating/consolidating the emotional requirements for several types of users including older adults, formal and informal caregivers. Addition-

⁵ A pilot study is a small-scale test of a method to be used on a larger scale

⁶ Information on how each pilot has elicited its requirements can be found in [12]

ally, we describe how the process has been used to analyze the requirements for the PHArA-ON ecosystem, and we briefly discuss how such requirements were used to derive design solutions and the proposed methods for their evaluation.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows; we briefly describe the PHArA-ON project in Section 2. Section 3 describes the process for dealing with emotional requirements, and Section 4 discusses how the process has been applied to deal with the requirements for the PHArA-ON ecosystem with special emphasis on emotional requirements. In Section 5, we present our findings and lessons learned, and related work is presented in Section 6. Finally, we conclude the paper and discuss future work in Section 7.

2 The PHArA-ON Project

Given the preference of older adults to remain in their own homes, compounded by the scarcity of caregivers and the expenses associated with home care nursing, there is an increasing demand for smart solutions to assist the well-being and active aging of older adults. With this in mind, the main aim of PHArA-ON⁷ (Pilots for Healthy and Active Ageing in Europe), an H2020 European project, is to actualize smart and active living for Europe’s aging population, and make such smart and active living a reality [12]. To achieve this ambitious goal, the PHArA-ON consortium has pinpointed several critical challenges (presented in table 1) that need to be addressed. Addressing these challenges entails leveraging advanced services, devices, and tools to forge an integrated and highly customizable interoperable open platform—the PHArA-ON ecosystem. This ecosystem will be crafted by harnessing platforms, technologies, and tools provided by consortium members or developed by third parties through open calls.

The primary users of the PHArA-ON ecosystem encompass older adults, healthcare professionals, and both formal and informal caregivers. Accordingly, a user-centric approach [13] has been followed for developing the PHArA-ON ecosystem, which will equip its users with the right tools and technologies that enable them to utilize different services from different providers focusing on well-being, socialization, training, etc. In this context, a pivotal success determinant for the PHArA-ON ecosystem lies in capturing the requirements of its users and stakeholders. These requirements will be used as a foundation for defining the core functionalities and qualities of the ecosystem. Emphasis is particularly placed on emotional requirements, recognizing their critical role in ensuring the usability and acceptance of the PHArA-ON ecosystem. These requirements have been specified, mainly, by six different pilots (Spain (Murcia and Andalusia), Portugal, the Netherlands, Slovenia, and Italy), where each pilot concentrates on a subset of the identified challenges. The PHArA-ON ecosystem will be tested and validated in two stages: pre-validation and large-scale pilots (LSPs) validation within these six pilots. These comprehensive validation phases aim to ensure the efficacy and readiness of the ecosystem for broader implementation.

⁷ <https://www.pharaon.eu/>

Table 1. PHArA-ON key Challenges (PCH)

ID	Description
PCH1	The behavior and the approach of elderly to friendly technological devices
PCH2	Health status definition and its progress over time
PCH3	Non-intrusive monitoring and alarm triggering
PCH4	Promote social cohesion
PCH5	Define specific personalized care plan on the basis of user's needs
PCH6	Reduce loneliness and enhance autonomy through connectivity and digital tools
PCH7	Promote accessibility and provision of proximity services through IT platforms
PCH8	Promote capacity building and awareness on citizenship and cultural traditions
PCH9	Indoor environmental quality
PCH10	Support to caregivers toward more efficient and personalized care services

3 A Process for Engineering Emotional Requirements

The process for engineering the emotional requirements (depicted in Figure 1) consists of four main interrelated activities that have been constructed based on the human-centered design approach proposed in the ISO 9241 [13]:

1. Specifying the context of use: aims at identifying relevant users⁸ and stakeholders of the ecosystem; their characteristics; their goals and tasks as well as the characteristics of tasks that can influence usability and accessibility. Consequently, two sub-activities must be conducted: *1.1 Users & stakeholders analysis:* aims at understanding the overall scope of the ecosystem by identifying all users and stakeholders that may influence or be influenced by the ecosystem, and classifying them into coherent groups to better identify their needs and expectations concerning the ecosystem. *1.2 Users & stakeholders goals, tasks and expectations analysis:* aims to identify the goals and expectations of the identified groups concerning the services to be provided by the ecosystem. A pre-analysis of the target ecosystem and an analysis of existing/similar systems/ecosystems along with other sources can be used as input to specify key user and stakeholder groups as well as their goals. These sub-activities produce the *context-of-use description*, which should be described in sufficient detail to support the requirements, design, and evaluation activities.

2. Specifying users and stakeholders requirements (USRs): In a software ecosystem, the integration of disparate software components or subsystems, each developed by distinct entities, presents a series of interconnected challenges, herein termed as *problems*. The entities tasked with eliciting the requirements to address these challenges are referred to as *Consortium Members (CMs)*. This activity comprises several sub-activities:

2.1 Identifying CMs relevant problems: aims at assigning key ecosystem *problems* to different *CMs* based on their characteristics and the *problem's* nature. Specifically, each CM should identify the stakeholders and users relevant to its assigned problems, then, elicit requirements related to these problems. This activity should ensure that all identified problems are assigned to CMs.

⁸ Users are a subset of stakeholders, we differentiate between the two as users are the main source for eliciting emotional requirements

Fig. 1. A process for engineering emotional requirements

2.2 Designing user and stakeholders requirements (USRs) elicitation method: Following the identification of their respective problems, each CM is tasked with devising an appropriate method for eliciting USRs. We recommend co-creation/co-design workshops/sessions aligned with the motivational goal modeling technique [3], which produces the following four lists: *Do* (functional goals), *Be* (quality goals), *Feel* (emotional goals), and *Who* (stakeholder roles). However, any traditional elicitation methods (e.g., interviews, surveys) can be used if adapted to produce the aforementioned four lists.

2.3 Conducting the USRs elicitation: Once the USRs elicitation method is established, the method should be strictly followed during the elicitation of USRs. While each CM takes charge of designing and executing the USRs elicitation specific to their designated problem(s), the resulting elicitation report must adopt a standardized format across all CMs. This standardization facilitates the derivation of comprehensive USRs for the entire ecosystem. It also aids in identifying and reconciling potential conflicts among these requirements. Ultimately, this uniformity streamlines the process of deriving design solutions that can be easily integrated.

2.4 Deriving USRs: The elicitation reports obtained from the preceding activity contain the initial version of the USRs in terms of three sets of goals (functional, quality, and emotional), which might lack consistency, or missing inter-relationships among these goals. Consequently, these issues are dealt with in this activity, and the reports should be carefully checked and used to elicit USRs for the overall ecosystem and present them in a uniform format (e.g., a well-structured unified template is highly advised) that allows their review and validation.

2.5 Prioritizing and Validating USRs: Aims to gather user and stakeholder feedback on the compiled list of USRs to effectively prioritize and validate them. The selection of prioritization techniques can vary based on the system/ecosystem's characteristics. Techniques such as Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), Cumulative Voting, Ranking, Ten Requirements, or Numerical Assignment (Grouping) can be chosen to suit the system's specific attributes. The requirements validation process encompasses three key activities outlined in [1]: 1. *Completeness checks:* Ensure that the requirements comprehensively capture all system functionalities, properties, constraints expected by the users and stakeholders; 2. *Consistency checks:* Verify the absence of conflicting requirements, ensuring there are no contradictions or discrepancies among them; and 3. *Realism checks:* Verify that the requirements can be implemented.

2.6 USRs refinement and update: Occurs after activity 3 and aims at refining and updating the USRs list based on the received feedback, which may suggest relaxing or refining some USRs to better fit the users' needs, modified to better match the technology chosen to realize them. It is important to note that 2.6 is an iterative activity that might be repeated several times until the USRs list attains a level where further refinement is unnecessary.

2.7 Consolidating the final list of USRs: It takes the updated USRs list that resulted from the 2.6 activity as input, then, applies the three checks we used in 2.5 (*completeness, consistency, and realism check*) to them, which will result in the final consolidated USRs list.

3. Producing design solutions: It is comprised of two sub-activities: 3.1 *Deriving design solutions:* that takes the validated/consolidated USRs and derives the reference architecture of the overall ecosystem in terms of its main components. 3.2 *Altering design solutions based on evaluation results:* is needed when the evaluation results show that design solutions do not meet USRs. In such cases, this sub-activity tries to refine/alternate design solutions to meet USRs.

4. Evaluating the design: In ISO 9241 [13], two widely used methods of user-centered evaluation can be employed: 1- *user-based testing* can be carried out to assess whether usability objectives, including measurable usability performance and satisfaction criteria, have been met in the intended context(s) of use. 2- *inspection-based evaluation* is ideally performed by usability experts who put themselves into the role of the user. Regardless of the adopted evaluation method, a clear evaluation and acceptance criteria for the evaluation should be defined.

4 Applying the Process for Engineering the Emotional Requirements for the PHArA-ON Ecosystem

This section provides a detailed description of how the process has been used to engineer the requirements for the PHArA-ON ecosystem with special emphasis on emotional requirements.

1. Specifying the context of use: started with *1.1 Users & stakeholders analysis*, in which, we depend on the PHArA-ON proposal and analysis of existing/similar [eco]systems as input to identify key users and stakeholders groups. These encompassed older adults, healthcare professionals, formal and informal caregivers. Following this, we conducted *1.2 Users & stakeholders goals, tasks & expectations analysis*, in which, we analyzed each of these groups to identify their goals and expectations concerning the services to be provided by the PHArA-ON ecosystem. Both of these sub-activities contributed to the *context-of-use description*, which identifies, besides user and stakeholder groups and objectives, the physical, technical, and social aspects of the overall ecosystem. This detailed description aids in delineating the ecosystem boundary and defining its ‘sub-systems’, along with their respective boundaries and interdependencies. Such clarity is essential to facilitate seamless integration among these ‘sub-systems’.

2. Specifying users and stakeholders requirements (USRs): consists of the following sub-activities:

2.1 Identifying pilots’ relevant challenges: Drawing from the *context-of-use description*, the PHArA-ON CHallenges (PCH), representing the *problems*, have been allocated to different pilots, which represent the *Consortium Members (CMs)* responsible for eliciting requirements relevant to these PCHs. Due to space constraints, our focus will be directed solely toward the activities of one pilot (Andalusia), which has been assigned two PCHs: *PCH₄* and *PCH₆*.

2.2 Designing User Requirements (USRs) Elicitation Method: The intended approach for eliciting user requirements within the PHArA-ON project involved co-creation/co-design workshops/sessions [14], conducted in the format of motivational goal model workshops [3]. However, due to the prevalence of the COVID-19 virus, only the Netherlands pilot conducted a physical co-design workshop. The remaining pilots resorted to virtual co-design/co-creation sessions, alongside phone and online interviews. Still, all these elicitation methods were adapted to produce the same output prescribed in [3], consisting of Do/Be/Feel/Who lists, which are then structured as motivational goal models.

Regarding the Andalusian pilot, initially, three co-design workshops were scheduled, involving care professionals, older adults with varying levels of technology experience, and those without such experience. However, due to the COVID-19 outbreak, these workshops had to be transformed into online sessions. They were restructured as individual semi-structured phone interviews conducted with the same three groups, all on a voluntary participation basis. The interviews with older adults were structured into several sections: 1- Obtaining informed consent and providing general project information, and the specific challenges within the pilot, 2- Collecting socio-demographic information, 3- Exploring their typical daily routine, 4- Discussing their interaction with technology, 5- Discussing how technology could enhance their everyday experiences, and 6- a pool of questions (a subset is shown in Table 2) for eliciting their requirements (*functional*, *quality* and *emotional* goals). Interviews with professionals consist of the same sections but are adapted to professionals' points of view.

2.3 Conducting the USRs elicitation: As previously mentioned, regardless of the selected elicitation method, it should produce the following four lists: *Do* (functional goals); *Be* (quality goals); *Feel* (emotional goals); and *Who* (stakeholder roles). Followingly, Do/Be/Feel/Who lists, representing the *elicitation report*, were hierarchically structured as motivational goal models [3]. In motivational goal model, *goals* represent the objectives/aims of [eco]system users, and it can be *functional*, *quality*, or *emotional*. *Functional goals* are based on motives, and describe an intended state of affairs a performer of a particular role wants to/can achieve. A *functional goal* can consist of sub-goals, where these sub-goals contribute to achieving the higher-level goal. *Quality goals* and *emotional goals* are attached to *functional goals*, where the first describe required *qualities* that should be maintained, and the last describe desired emotions of

Table 2. Partial phone interview guide - Goals Model section - Andalusia

TO DO Goals - (Functional goal) - <i>What it should do?</i>
What hobbies would you like to share with other people?
What kind of activity reminders would you like the solution to have?
What kind of entertainment would you like the system would offer you?
What kind of people would you like to be connected with?
TO BE Goals - (Quality Goal) - <i>How it should be?</i>
How should the information be represented in the system (e.g., text, voice)?
Which type of messages best fit your interest?
Would you like to see other people? Or just hear them?
Would you like the system to take your preferences into account?
TO FEEL Goals - (Emotional goal) - <i>How it should feel?</i>
How would you feel if you could talk to people you've never seen/heard before?
How would you feel if the system informed you of social/cultural events?
How would you feel with a device that allows you to connect with similar people and propose meetings/appointments?
Are there any negative emotions that might be related to using a technology to meet people? What fears do you have?

relevant *role*, which represents a user (group of users) of the system that can be characterized by capacities and responsibilities that are needed for the achievement of functional goals.

Concerning the Andalusian pilot, the result of the interviews carried out with different users and stakeholders groups to specify their needs have been constructed in the form of a motivational goal model (Figure 2). Specifically, the model is developed starting with specifying the top-level functional goal, which represents the main objective/goal the system needs to achieve. Then, the top-level goal is refined into sub-goals, which in turn, can be also refined into more refined sub-goals. After that, the roles, quality goals, and emotional goals are attached to relevant functional goals. The main functional goal of the motivational goal model, representing the purpose of the sociotechnical system - Support wellbeing - has been elaborated into three sub-goal: *Improving digital skills*, *Participating in the community*, and *Providing cognitive stimulation*, which are characterized by several quality and emotional goals. Each of the three functional goals has been further refined into three additional motivational goal models, which we could not include in this paper.

Fig. 2. The motivational goal model for the Andalusian pilot of supporting well-being of older adults

2.4 Deriving USRs: The motivational goal models generated in the preceding stage have been carefully checked and used to elicit the USRs and represent them as use case scenarios. A standardized format in the form of tables was adopted for uniformity across all pilots. An example of these scenarios related to the Andalusian pilot is presented in Table 3. Each scenario is described by a *number* for identification purposes, a *goal* corresponding to one of the key functional goals identified in the motivational goal model, an *initiator* that acts to trigger the scenario, and a *description*. Each scenario is composed of several *activities*, described in the *activity* field, and may have a *condition* that can be: *interleaved* means a set of activities may be performed in any order; *sequence* means a set of activities need to be performed one after another, and *optional*

Table 3. Improving digital skills Scenario - Andalusian Pilot

Scenario 1					
Goal	Improve digital skills				
Initiator	Volunteer				
Trigger	An action by the volunteer				
Description	allows older adults to train their digital skills to promote the use of technology to facilitate digital inclusion and eradicate digital divide in Andalusia				
Condition	Step	Activity	Roles	Quality goals	Emotional goals
Sequence	1	The older adult provides information about his or her digital skills and education level for assessing the digital skills	Older Adult, Volunteer	Interactive, Easy to use, Guiding, Helpful	Included, Amused, Empowered
	2	A volunteer schedules offline classes for the older adult			
-	-	-	-	-	-

when performing an activity is not mandatory. *Steps* play a role when activities have a sequence to follow. The fifth and sixth columns respectively list *quality goal(s)* and *emotional goals(s)* represented by the motivational goal model.

2.5 Prioritizing and Validating USRs: Following, the numerical assignment prioritization technique, the USRs was structured around three priority levels: *priority 1* indicates a requirement that needs to be implemented, but at the moment it has a low priority for the given pilot; *priority 2* indicates a requirement that needs to be implemented, even if it is not the first priority of the given pilot; and *priority 3* indicates a requirement that has the maximum priority for the given pilot. While various methods were employed across pilots to prioritize their USRs, adherence to these predefined priority levels was mandatory.

Regarding the *validation of USRs*, this process was overseen by a member of the PHArA-ON consortium, the University of Tartu. After collating the USRs lists from all pilots in the specified format, the validation followed a structured approach described in [1], comprising three key activities: 1. *completeness check* was conducted by checking whether the lists of USRs identified by pilots capture all the functionalities and characteristics (qualities and emotions) the ecosystem is expected to deliver. During this check, we contacted several pilots for additional information and clarifications when there were issues concerning missing USRs. After that, we asked each pilot to check the elaborated list of USRs again. Some pilots asked to add new USRs that were not included in the list, refine some existing USRs, and even delete some USRs as they were considered out of the ecosystem scope or covered by more refined USRs. When the overall USRs list was considered complete concerning the users' and stakeholders' needs, we conducted the 2. *consistency checks* the objective of which was to identify and resolve conflicts among the USRs, where a conflict is a situation when two or more requirements cannot be achieved together. This check was able to detect some conflicts, which we managed to resolve by revising the conflicting USRs with the help of corresponding pilot(s). After the overall USRs list was verified as consistent, we conducted the 3. *realism checks* mainly with pilots together with technology providers. As previously mentioned, USRs were accompanied by po-

tential implementation technologies, which facilitated this check. No significant issues were identified due to the nature of the PHArA-ON project - being an Innovation Action - to combine and integrate technological solutions rather than developing new solutions from scratch.

2.6 USRs update and refinement: occurred after activity 3, where the project made several progresses. Notably, a comprehensive analysis of the overall PHArA-ON ecosystem was conducted, concretizing its constituent components, and defining its reference architecture. Additionally, the pilots significantly enhanced their understanding of the anticipated services and technologies. Consequently, the initially specified USRs had to be updated to reflect these advancements. Therefore, each pilot was tasked with identifying any modifications (e.g., additions, alterations, removals of requirements) to their initial USRs. Primarily, the changes centered around technology specifications—either due to certain technologies failing to meet project requirements or the consideration of newer, more suitable alternatives. Furthermore, some modifications involved refining USRs with more specific, detailed information, alongside updates in the requirement priorities. Additionally, we transformed USRs into the user stories format [15], as such format is easy to specify, understand, revise, and most importantly, it facilitates the communication between technical and non-technical stakeholders, i.e., it allows cross-team clarity on what to develop, for whom, and why. We suggest the following format of user stories⁹:

As a **<performer of some Role>**, I want/shall be able to perform **<some action>**, using **<some technology>**, to achieve **<some goal>**[, with the consideration of **<some quality goal>**], so that achieving **<some emotional goal>**]

Table 4 presents an updated USR in the user stories format. To facilitate traceability, all IDs of the USRs use the following format: PUCS_PilotIDScenarioID.ActivityNumber.USRID, where the PUCS prefix stands for the initials of PHArA-ON Use Case Scenario, and PUCS_A01.1.001 means that the user story was elicited by the Andalusian pilot (A), from the first Scenario (01) and the first activity in that scenario (1), with ID 001.

⁹ The inclusion of quality and emotional goals in user stories is optional (indicated by square brackets [...]) since not all user goals have associated quality/emotional goals

Table 4. An example of an updated USR as a user story - Andalusian Pilot

Req. ID	Requirements as a user story	Priority
PUCS_A01.1.001	As an <older adult> , I <should be able to provide information about my digital skills and education level> , using <an App deployed in a Tablet> , to achieve <improve digital skills> with the consideration of < guided and ease of use > so that achieving < amused and empowered >	2

2.7 Consolidating the final list of USRs: We took the list of USRs as user stories as an input, then, we rigorously applied the same three validation checks (*completeness, consistency, and realism checks*) utilized in 2.5, where pilots were asked to check and verify the USRs again to ensure that there were no missing or wrong details introduced during the transformation process. The received feedback contains suggestions to revise several USRs, which were corrected accordingly. The outcome of this activity has been used to update the design solutions that have been initially derived based on the validated USRs resulting from activity 2.5.

3. Producing design solutions: is composed of two sub-activities: *3.1 Deriving design solutions:* in the initial iteration following Activity 2.5, we outlined the reference architecture (high-level design solutions) of the PHArA-ON ecosystem based on the validated USRs. As the PHArA-ON ecosystem will, mostly, consist of a series of software components that will be delivered by the PHArA-ON partners or via open calls, this activity mapped USRs to these components, and when there is no available component to realize a USR, such USR was marked as to be realized by solution/technology to be provided by third-parties via an open call. Subsequently, in the second iteration after Activity 2.7, the reference architecture was updated based on the refined and consolidated USRs. Here, the open calls resulted in solutions/technologies sourced from third-party providers. An illustrative example of USR-to-design solution mapping is detailed in Table 5. Please note that the mapping was done for the functional requirements, and relevant quality and emotional requirements were derived from the related scenario using the Scenario ID. *3.2 Altering design solutions based on evaluation results:* will refine design solutions based on the received evaluation results.

4. Evaluating the design: following ISO 9241 [13], *user-based testing* has been adopted as the evaluation method, where developed solutions are evaluated against USRs. This activity covered all USRs, yet we focus on emotional requirements due to space limitations. The following evaluation method has been drafted, and is followed when assessing the satisfaction of emotional requirements. *Evaluation method:* pilots will analyze the list of the emotional goals identified in the consolidated USRs, then, each pilot will decide whether a *quantitative* and/or *qualitative evaluation method* is appropriate for collecting feedback from end-users to allow the assessment of the satisfaction of emotional requirements. Concerning the *quantitative evaluation*, two types of questionnaires have been designed: 1- *Standard questionnaire:* that will include the most appropriate tools for the assessment of emotional requirements.

Table 5. An example of mapping a USR to design solutions - Andalusian Pilot

Scenario ID	Activity	Functional Requirement	Technologies
PUCS_A01	Participant's digital skills profile	Older adult should be able to fill in a template user profile on the tablet	SentabTV, OneSait
		Interactions of older adult with the tablet and the platform should be facilitated by "text to speech"	

The identification of these tools was done by investigating various domains to select the most relevant tools/measures for the assessment of emotional requirements depending on their nature. For example, PSS (Perceived Stress Scale) [16] was selected to assess *Relaxed & Less stressed*, Item 9 from the System Usability Scale (SUS) [17] was selected to assess *Confidence*, UCLA Loneliness Scale [18] was selected to assess *Connected & Involved*, MSC (Most Significant Change) [19] was selected to assess *Engaged, Integrated & Stimulated*, and Lubben Social Network Scale [20] was selected to assess *Engaged & Involved*. 2- *Ad-hoc questionnaire*: designed to collect feedback from end-users taking into consideration the emotional requirements included in the USRs. A partial ad-hoc questionnaire is shown in Table 6. Concerning the *qualitative evaluation*, focus groups/individual interviews that represent target user groups are used to verify how the satisfaction of emotional requirements were perceived.

5 Findings and Lessons Learned

Through using our process for dealing with the requirements for the PHArA-ON ecosystem with special emphasis on emotional requirements, we have faced several challenges related to the different activities we performed. In what follows, we summarize our findings, suggestions, and lessons learned:

Considering co-creation workshops (or co-design sessions) for the elicitation of emotional requirements: co-creation approaches empower users and stakeholders while specifying their needs/requirements, especially, the emotional ones. Specifically, they give users a voice and treat them as active contributors. This increases their involvement in the requirements identification process, which is a key success factor for the adoption and usage of the resulting ecosystem as it will shape it based on their needs/requirements. However, successful co-creation workshops require the involvement of all key relevant users and stakeholders.

Capturing emotional requirements: is usually done relying on traditional psychological methods such as self-reporting and observation-based, which

Table 6. A partial ad-hoc questionnaire for assessing emotional requirements

Domain		User Code:				
Open Question		How do you feel using the PHArA-ON System?				
After using the PHArA-ON system, do you feel (answer from 1 to 5):						
Emotion	Description	S. disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	S. agree
Stressed	Less stressed by the usage of the Technology?	1	2	3	4	5
Informed	More aware of your health situation?	1	2	3	4	5
Empowered	Do you have increased opportunities for socialization?	1	2	3	4	5

heavily rely on participant cooperation and are subject to human biases [8]. However, recent technologies such as wearable technologies, if available, could overcome such limitations allowing direct collection of affective states representing emotions.

Considering motivational goal models as the artifact resulting from co-creation workshops: a co-creation workshop results, usually, in visual artifacts and documentation concerning the [eco]system to be developed. Such artifacts/documentation should facilitate capturing knowledge generated during the workshop and documenting it in a way that allows its understanding and review by involved entities. Accordingly, using motivational goal models as an artifact to capture, present, and document users' (and stakeholders') needs is highly advised. Using motivational goal model in the PHArA-ON project has proven that it is easy to develop, understood, and very suitable for facilitating communications between technical and non-technical stakeholders.

Considering dependencies between functional, quality, and emotional requirements: motivational goal models can explicitly capture such dependencies, yet most other goal-modeling languages do not. Therefore, if a language other than motivational goal models was adopted, it is strongly advised to extend it with such dependencies.

Considering user stories (US) as a [final] format for requirements: US mostly capture user-visible functional requirements, therefore, they face various challenges when dealing with quality and emotional requirements, as emotional requirements are first-class citizens and not subsumed under NFRs. We solve this problem by proposing a flexible template that allows for explicitly capturing the relationship between functional requirements and their associated emotional and quality requirements, which was essential to be captured in many cases. Specifically, this will ensure that emotional requirements will not be overlooked in the final solution.

Mapping requirements to implementation technologies: Most ecosystems are built by modifying/extending software solutions, then, integrating them rather than building new solutions from scratch. The PHArA-ON ecosystem is no exception, thus, we have mapped the requirements to existing software solutions provided by the consortium members or by third parties. This facilitate performing the *realism check* while validating/consolidating the requirements and, in turn, deriving/updating the reference architecture for the PHArA-ON ecosystem. Concerning emotional requirements, they were not mapped directly to implementation technologies since most of them were not expected to be realized by a single technology but a set of them.

Managing the validation of emotional requirements: Unlike functional and many types of quality requirements, there are no agreed-upon methods for validating emotional requirements [6]. Consequently, we have to devise a method for the validation of emotional requirements that considers both *quantitative* and/or *qualitative evaluation methods*, which have been constructed based on the pilots' experience as well as adopting various well-known tools to be used for the assessment of emotional requirements.

6 Related work

There are relatively few approaches for dealing with emotional requirements. For instance, Miller et al. [3] propose preliminary work on including emotions in requirements models using emotional goals. Their work was evaluated in a controlled user study, and by applying it to an emergency system for older adults case study. Grundy et al. [9] proposed a model-driven approach to model various human-centric aspects/requirements including emotions. The authors plan to extend their work to cover code generation relying on these models in their future work. Iqbal et al. [4] propose a methodology compatible with the theory of constructed emotion for designing and developing emotive software artifacts. Apart from requirements, Seligman [21] proposes the PERMA (Positive emotions, Engagement, positive Relationships, Meaning, and Accomplishments) framework that offers elements required to facilitate well-being. According to the author, PERMA is not an exhaustive framework, and it could be expanded.

7 Conclusions and future work

We introduce an RE process specifically tailored for handling emotional requirements. The process has been developed within the context of the PHArA-ON project and has been successfully used for dealing with the emotional requirements of the PHArA-ON ecosystem. We aimed to make the process easy to follow, and we accompanied each of its activities with a detailed description of how it can be conducted. On the other hand, this research has uncovered several critical research gaps, laying the groundwork for potential future work. For instance, motivational goal models capture emotional requirements at a high abstract level, and lack a systematic process for their refinement. They also overlook various types of dependencies among requirements (e.g., requires), which we consider essential for appropriately dealing with emotional requirements. Finally, dealing with emotional states might have ethical implications, which we aim to investigate in future research. An area of concern in our process involves the potential threat to validity due to the *generalization of findings* validity since it was applied to one ecosystem. However, we intend to validate the process further by applying it to various case studies spanning different domains.

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